

Toward lightweight hand tracking systems

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Abstract—The usage of human demonstrations facilitates teaching of objects manipulation to robots. The article suggests a new non invasive approach to gather manipulation demonstrations and proposes a platform to study and develop the needed technologies.

Index Terms—IMU, Sensory Glove, Motion Capture, Human Demonstration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future intelligent robots are expected to operate in human environments and physically interact with object designed for humans, objects that should be manipulated according to their physical characteristics such as fragility and affordance. A truly autonomous robot should therefore be equipped with robust policies for object manipulation and with the ability to adapt such policies to unknown objects or, if necessary, learn new policies. With this intent, different approaches have been explored in the literature to learn such policies from human demonstration. In particular, multimodal data from human interaction with objects have been proposed to learn how to grasp and manipulate objects [1], data from a smart glove, equipped with magnetic trackers, have been used to learn grasp strategies [2] and human demonstrations, recorded in virtual reality, have been used to improve reinforcement learning results in manipulation tasks [3]. Data extracted from human demonstration usually refers to hand motion and tactile information. On the one hand, the perception of hand motion has been studied in different scenarios and for different applications. RGB-D cameras, such as Kinect or Leap Motion, and motion capture systems (mocap), based either on active or passive markers, have been used to this aim. These systems need a structured environment, since their sensitivity to lighting conditions and occlusions, and constrain the workspace. However, in order to record informative demonstrations the teacher should be able to operate without limitations imposed by the workspace. On the other hand, tactile information is usually perceived using sensorized objects [1]. Tactile sensors [4] can be embodied into objects with regular shapes and big enough to contain the necessary electronics but the sensorization of daily life object can be challenging or even impossible. An alternative approach to record human manipulation demonstrations can be the usage of data gloves. Different kinds of gloves exist, but the most common one perceives the hand motion using flex sensors [7] or Inertial Measurement Units

Fig. 1. The data glove equipped with 12 IMUs, the MCU collecting the data and 14 reflective markers for the Optitrack mocap.

(IMUs) [6]. Furthermore, data gloves can be equipped with tactile sensors thus avoiding the object sensorization problem. This solution does not achieve the precision of marker based motion capture systems but removes workspace constraints. Nevertheless, systems based on gloves can alter the human demonstration by constraining the hand motion and reducing the tactile feedback. Especially for the IMU-based approach, the glove presence is not fundamental. Therefore, it is possible to envision a solution in which IMUs, tactile sensors, Micro Controller Units (MCUs), bluetooth modules and batteries are embodied in a set of rings or similar objects, and the hand tracking is performed using all of them. In fact, commercial products implementing some of these specifications already exist such as Motiv Ring by Motiv¹. However, to design and develop a similar system many challenges should be faced both from the hardware and software perspective. In this paper, we propose an open source data glove to develop and test software solutions for IMU-based hand tracking.

The article presents a preliminary hardware implementation, the related software architecture and some tracking results for the data glove. Furthermore, results obtained using the glove prototype are compared with a setup using a standard motion capture system.

¹www.mymotiv.com

Fig. 2. Hand skeleton visualisation result from the two perception modality and the mocap system.

II. HARDWARE

The data glove is equipped with 12 6-axis IMUs (3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope each) located as shown in Fig. 1. Each finger is tracked by two IMUs, one on the intermediate phalanx and one on the proximal one. Furthermore, two IMUs are devoted to track the hand back and the wrist. The IMUs used for this prototype are the MPU-6050 from InvenSense providing a digital output through an I2C bus. The MCU used to control all the sensors is the MKR 1010, equipped with a WiFi module. To preserve the hand mobility and sensitivity a thin and flexible glove has been selected as support. To reduce their impact on the hand motion the IMUs are not directly glued on the glove but 3D printed mountings have been used. The finger mountings consist of a half ring structure while for the hand back an L-shaped support has been used. The wrist IMU and the MCU are mounted on a rectangular support fixed to the arm with a velcro strap. All the hand mountings have been printed using a flexible resin while for the wrist mount ABS material has been used. In Fig. 1 can be noticed that each IMU is paired with one spherical reflective marker, three for the hand back. The markers are tracked by 7 Flex 3 cameras by OptiTrack² showed in Fig. 2 (c).

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The software architecture is distributed among three devices. The MCU performs the startup procedures to properly set the IMUs and samples the IMUs data. Because of the nature of the I2C bus, the sampling procedure should be performed sequentially. Each time a sample is acquired, the MCU sends it to a workstation through Wi-Fi using the UDP protocol. The motion capture cameras are connected through USB to a PC running the OptiTrack proprietary software Motive, which streams the tracking results to the PC using a socket-based communication. On the central PC, IMUs data are processed by a Kalman Filter [5] to extract roll and pitch for each link. Mocap data are checked to prevent errors due to occlusions

or spurious markers. Fig. 2 represents the skeleton obtained by the IMUs data, visualised using a MATLAB toolbox [8], the mocap data and the mocap system. The IMUs data consist of the assets of each link, while the mocap ones consist of the 3D position of the barycenter of each link. To perform the comparison it is possible, knowing the hand size, to compute the hand joints angles from the two sources of information.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The article presents a data glove using IMUs to perform hand tracking and describes its hardware and software. Moreover, a methodology to validate the tool, using a vision-based mocap, is described. Although a quantitative comparison has not been performed yet, the preliminary results suggest that the glove is apt for hand tracking. Future work will aim to improve both the hardware, in the direction of the standalone rings, and the software, reducing communication delays and tracking errors.

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²www.optitrack.com